

Hydrophobic and aromatic polymer nanofibers for a spin-filter micro solid phase extraction of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in river water

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ABSTRACT

The use of hydrophobic and aromatic polymer nanofibers as novel sorbents for extracting polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) from river water has been evaluated. Of the materials tested, the biodegradable aliphatic polymer polycaprolactone (PCL) exhibited strong retention of all analytes via hydrophobic interactions. In contrast, the aromatic polymer polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) demonstrated superior performance with higher-ring PAHs due to a combination of hydrophobic and π - π stacking interactions. The porous, permeable structure of the fibrous sorbents enabled rapid extraction. The spin-filter μ SPE format required only 10 s for sorbent activation, extraction, and elution, resulting in a total processing time of 30 s per sample. Up to 48 samples could be processed simultaneously, reducing manual handling and simplifying the workflow. Analytical performance was evaluated using river water spiked at different concentration levels. The method showed good linearity ($R^2 \geq 0.98$) across concentration ranges of 0.1–5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for most analytes, with limits of detection of 0.009–0.14 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for PCL and 0.012–0.27 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for PPS. Recoveries ranged from 57 to 102 % for PCL and 88–139 % for PPS, with relative standard deviations below 15 %, and preconcentration factors of approximately twofold. These results demonstrate that meltblown PCL and PPS nanofibers combined with spin-filter μ SPE provide a rapid and practical approach to extracting PAHs from environmental water samples.

1. Introduction

The extensive use of fossil fuels and industrial emissions has led to the widespread release of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) into the environment. These persistent organic pollutants accumulate in sediments and can leach into aquatic systems. Due to their carcinogenic, mutagenic, and toxic properties they pose serious risks to human health, marine organisms, and ecosystems [1–4,5]. PAHs are difficult to detect because they are barely soluble in water and typically occur at trace concentrations, and their reliable detection remains challenging [6]. Effective monitoring therefore requires preconcentration strategies to enable sensitive and accurate analysis. In recent years, various methods have been developed to extract and preconcentrate PAHs from water. These methods cover solid phase extraction (SPE) [7,8], on-line SPE [9], pipette-tip solid-phase microextraction [10], in-syringe μ -SPE [11], and SPE using centrifugation [12]. While these approaches offer adequate sensitivity, many require relatively large amounts of sorbent, multiple

handling steps, long extraction times, or specialized equipment. These factors can limit sample throughput and hinder the practicality for routine monitoring. Consequently, miniaturized extraction techniques have gained increasing attention because they reduce solvent and sorbent consumption, shorten extraction times, and simplify workflows. In this context, spin-filter microextraction is an attractive alternative because it combines rapid mass transfer, minimal handling, and compatibility with parallel sample processing. This makes it well-suited for fast and efficient PAHs analysis in environmental waters.

Centrifugation is used in solid phase extraction (SPE) to propel samples and solvents through a sorbent. This process is known as spin column micro solid phase extraction (SC- μ SPE). Careful control of rotor speed is essential to ensure efficient analyte retention [13,14]. Originally designed for sample filtration and DNA purification, these devices have recently gained attention as extraction tools. Similar to conventional SPE, the process can be exhaustive or nearly exhaustive, but it requires significantly smaller amounts of sorbent and organic solvent.

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Although the column must be repeatedly placed in the centrifuge repeatedly and reloaded manually after each step (loading the sample, washing, and eluting), this configuration reduces manipulation error and enhances trapping efficiency compared with other miniaturized formats such as pipette-tip μ -SPE [14]. Consequently, the cartridge-based design is easy to operate, requires only minimal sample and elution volumes, and eliminates the need for solvent evaporation. While this method has not yet been widely explored for extracting PAHs, several studies have demonstrated its strong performance with other analytes including dibucaine and naphazoline [15], organophosphorus pesticides [16], parabens [17], phthalate esters [18] and chlorophenols [19]. These findings suggest that spin column formats are promising as efficient, miniaturized extraction tools, and motivate their evaluation for hydrophobic, poorly soluble pollutants such as PAHs.

To maximize the potential of SC- μ SPE, it is crucial to select the appropriate sorbent material. Conventional packed sorbents often suffer from limited surface areas and slow mass transfer rates. In contrast, electrospun or meltblown polymer nanofibers offer relatively high surface-to-volume ratios, tunable porosity, and the ability to tailor chemical functionality via polymer selection or surface modification [20,21]. These features make nanofibrous materials highly attractive candidates for miniaturized extraction formats, where maximizing contact between the analyte and sorbent is essential [22,23]. Several studies have demonstrated the use of electrospun polymer nanofibers as sorbents for the extracting PAHs. For example, polyamide, polyacrylonitrile and carbon nanofibers functionalized with poly(dimethylsiloxane) have been used to enrich PAHs from water [9,24,25], while acrylonitrile butadiene styrene nanofiber film and polystyrene nanofibers functionalized with polydopamine and silver nanoparticles have been used to extract PAHs from human urine [26,27].

Different classes of polymers interact with PAHs in distinct ways, making them promising candidates for nanofiber sorbents. For example, polymers with aromatic backbones such as polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) and polybutylene terephthalate (PBT) exhibit strong hydrophobicity and enable π - π stacking interactions with PAH rings. Biodegradable polycaprolactone (PCL) has been used to extract lipophilic compounds because its long aliphatic backbones make it predominantly hydrophobic [28,29]. In a previous study, polyamide 11 (PA11) also demonstrated promising PAHs extraction attributed to its long hydrophobic aliphatic chains, which promote van der Waals and hydrophobic interactions with nonpolar analytes [9]. Polyimide (PI) have been shown to provide high extraction efficiency for PAHs, largely due to π - π interactions between the aromatic rings of the polymer and the analytes, as well as electron-donor interactions from the lone electron pairs of oxygen and nitrogen in the imide groups [30]. These structural features suggest that different polymer chemistries can be tailored to target PAHs through complementary interactions. However, their integration into spin column or filter μ SPE platforms remains unexplored.

For the first time, we developed a nanofiber-based spin-filter microextraction method to determine eight significant PAHs. We evaluated the use of nanofibrous discs prepared via electrospinning and meltblowing from various polymers, such as PCL, PPS, PBT, PA6, PA11, PI, and a polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB)/polypropylene (PP, 50:50) blend, as sorbents. The novelty of the method lies in combining meltblown polymer fibers and a rapid spin-filter μ SPE format. This combination enables short extraction times, parallel processing of multiple samples, and complementary retention mechanisms using aliphatic PCL and aromatic PPS fibers. Our method achieves high recoveries and low RSDs in real river water while minimizing sorbent and solvent consumption. Additionally, we evaluated the environmental impact using the AGREEprep greenness metric, which highlights the environmentally friendly nature of the method. This study also demonstrates the potential of using polymer nanofibers in spin-filter microextraction as a fast, simple, and reliable strategy for extracting hydrophobic pollutants from environmental waters.

2. Experimental

2.1. Reagents and chemicals

Standards of anthracene (ANT, purity $\geq 98\%$), pyrene (PYR, $\geq 98\%$), chrysene (CHR), benzo(k)fluoranthene (BkF, $\geq 99\%$), benzo(a)pyrene (BaP, $\geq 96\%$), dibenzo(a,h)anthracene (DahA), indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene (IcdP), benzo(g,h,i)perylene (BghiP, $\geq 98\%$) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Prague, Czech Republic). The characteristics of these analytes are presented in the Supplementary Materials section (Table S-1). Acetonitrile and methanol with an LC/MS purity grade $\geq 99.9\%$ were supplied by Biosolve (Dieuze, France). All chemicals were used as supplied, without any additional treatment. Ultrapure water with a conductivity of $0.055\ \mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at $25\ ^\circ\text{C}$ ($18.2\ \text{M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$) was prepared using a Milli-Q water system (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA).

2.2. Preparation of standards and samples

Stock solutions of all 8 analytes were prepared at a concentration of $2\ \text{mg}\ \text{L}^{-1}$ in acetonitrile and stored at $4\ ^\circ\text{C}$. The mixed standard solution was prepared at a concentration of $100\ \mu\text{g}\ \text{L}^{-1}$ and stored at $4\ ^\circ\text{C}$. A mixed standard solution for extraction optimization was prepared at a concentration of $5\ \mu\text{g}\ \text{L}^{-1}$ in 15% aqueous acetonitrile. Acetonitrile was added to improve the solubility of the hydrophobic analytes. A relatively high concentration was selected to ensure strong fluorescence responses and allows for a reliable comparison of extraction performance between different nanofibers during method development. Real water samples were collected from the Elbe River in November 2024. The samples were stored in pre-cleaned glass bottles at $4\ ^\circ\text{C}$ until analysis. Six parallel extractions were performed for each nanofiber material to minimize random error and ensure repeatability. The extractions were evaluated within a concentration range of 0.1 to $5\ \mu\text{g}\ \text{L}^{-1}$ in 15% aqueous acetonitrile. Percentage recovery was determined by comparing the peak areas of the extracted analytes to those obtained from the reference standard solution.

2.3. Instrumentation and software

Chromatographic analysis was performed using a Nexera UHPLC-FD system (Shimadzu Corporation, Japan), which was equipped with an SPD-M40 UV/VIS DAD detector, RF-20A X3 fluorescence detector a CBM-40 communication module, three LC-40B X3 solvent delivery modules, a SIL-40C X3 autosampler, and a CTO-40C column oven. Data evaluation and peak area integration were performed using Lab Solution software (Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). Extraction experiments were performed using MIKRO 220R centrifuge (Hettich, Germany).

2.4. Chromatographic analysis

An Ascentis Express 90A AQ-C18 column ($150\times 4.6\ \text{mm}$, $2.7\ \mu\text{m}$ particle size) from Supelco (Sigma-Aldrich) was used to separate the model analytes in the gradient mode at a column oven temperature of $30\ ^\circ\text{C}$. Acetonitrile, part A, and water, part B, were used as the components of the mobile phase. The following gradient elution was used for the separations: 0 – $7\ \text{min}$ 70 – 85% A in B, 7 – $9\ \text{min}$ 85% A, 9.01 – $11\ \text{min}$ 70% A. The flow rate was $1.5\ \text{mL}\ \text{min}^{-1}$ and the injection volume was $10\ \mu\text{L}$. Different excitation/emission wavelengths were set for each analyte in a switching wavelength program to obtain best sensitivity, [9,31]: 3.57 – $5.70\ \text{min}$ $260/400\ \text{nm}$ (ANT, PYR, CHR); 5.70 – $8.50\ \text{min}$ $294/430\ \text{nm}$ (BkF, DahA, BaP); 8.50 – $9.28\ \text{min}$ $250/490$ (IcdP); 9.28 – $11.00\ \text{min}$ $294/430$ (BghiP).

2.5. Fabrication of nanofibrous materials

We compared nanofibers made from the following polymers: PCL, PPS, PBT, PA6, PA11, PI, and a PHB:PP (50:50) blend. The structures of

the evaluated polymers are shown in Fig. 1. SEM images of PCL and PPS nanofibrous disc for spin filter extraction are shown in Fig. 2. Mats of these fibers were prepared using meltblowing (MB) and alternating current (AC) electrospinning technologies in cooperation with the Technical University Liberec. A detailed description and characterization of the nanofibrous materials, and their production can be found in the Supplementary material section (Nanofibers fabrication Fig. S-1, S-2, and Table S-2,3,4).

2.6. Extraction protocol

Discs with a diameter of 7.28 mm, and a thickness of around 3 mm were punched from the nanofiber mats using a stainless-steel circular press. The discs were placed in centrifugal plastic spin filters inside 2 mL Eppendorf tubes for phase collection. The disc diameter was chosen to match the bottom part of the tube for a proper fit. The extraction process consisted of three steps: (i) washing and activating the disc with 200 μ L organic solvent pipetted onto the disc surface, (ii) loading 600 μ L sample onto the disc, and (iii) eluting with 300 μ L acetonitrile. Centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 10 s followed each step. Washing and sample loading were done in one Eppendorf tube, and a new tube was used to collect the extract. A 10 μ L sample of the extract was injected into the UHPLC system for analysis. Fig. 3 shows the procedure for filling spin filter for microextraction with nanofibrous discs.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Selection of the polymer nanofibers

The evaluated analyte set consisted of eight PAHs that covered a wide polarity range ($\log P$ 3.9–7.7) and exhibited structural diversity ranging from three to six fused aromatic rings (Table S-1, Supplementary material). All the PAHs are hydrophobic and essentially planar, favoring hydrophobic and π - π stacking interactions [32]. We evaluated their retention efficiency on the nanofiber discs prepared by alternating current electrospinning and meltblowing from a variety of polymers. Polymers such as PPS, PBT, and PI contain aromatic groups in chains and were expected to exhibit stronger, more selective retention of the planar, higher-ring PAHs through combined π - π and hydrophobic interactions. In contrast, aliphatic polymers (PCL, PA11, PA6, and PHB:PP blend) lack π -conjugated domains and primarily rely on hydrophobic (van der Waals) interactions. Fig. 4 shows the heatmap of recoveries for the eight

analytes extracted using the different polymer nanofibers. Each row corresponds to a polymer type, and each column corresponds to an analyte. Colors represent relative recovery, ranging from the blue (lowest) to the red (highest). The numeric values within each cell indicate the mean recovery percentage (%) \pm RSD, calculated from six replicate extractions ($n = 6$). The full graphical dataset for all nanofibers is available in the Supplementary material (Fig. S-3).

No clear trend was observed between recovery and either analyte hydrophobicity ($\log P$) or the number of fused aromatic rings. Rather, extraction performance primarily depended on the chemical nature and morphology of the polymer nanofibers. Among the aliphatic nanofibers PCL showed the highest overall recovery with satisfactory repeatability. Both MB and AC PCL performed well, although MB PCL consistently outperformed AC PCL in terms of both recovery and reproducibility. This difference can be attributed to morphological factors: MB PCL had a looser, more fibrous (cotton-like) structure that was easier to cut into uniform discs for use in the spin filter format [33]. Despite their similar porosity ($\sim 90\%$), MB and AC PCL differed in markedly in fiber diameter and specific surface area (Table S-4, Supplementary Materials). The larger diameters of MB PCL fibers produced larger pore sizes and led to smaller surface area thus facilitating solvent penetration, analyte diffusion, and efficient desorption of PAHs. PA11 was another efficient performer, achieving recoveries between 85 and 98 % with low variability. Its long aliphatic chain structure imparts a hydrophobic character that enhances its affinity for PAHs through hydrophobic interactions. PA6 produced lower recoveries ($< 50\%$ for most analytes). Its hydrophilic nature, combined with swelling in acetonitrile, likely impaired extraction efficiency by limiting effective sorption and desorption. Blend polymer PHB:PP produced the poorest recovery rates across all analytes and exhibited high RSD values. This poor performance can be attributed to the brittle nature of the material, which complicated the process of cutting it into discs and resulted in less uniform sorbents. Additionally, the absence of aromatic groups in PHB:PP is likely to reduce interaction with PAHs, further impairing extraction. Among the aromatic nanofibers PBT performed well overall, with recoveries ranging from 60 to 92 %. The presence of aromatic terephthalate rings provides opportunities for π - π interactions, which explains its good performance across most analytes. PI showed selective behavior. It performed best with the smaller, planar PAHs, such as ANT and PYR. However, much lower recoveries were obtained with higher-ring-number compounds such as DahA (29 %) and BghiP (65 %). This suggests that although π - π interactions favor small, planar PAHs,

Fig. 1. Structures of the evaluated polymers.

Fig. 2. SEM images of PCL and PPS nanofibrous disc for spin filter extraction.

Fig. 3. Detailed depiction of the spin-filter filling process for the microextraction with nanofibrous discs.

	ANT	PYR	CHR	BKF	BAP	DaHa	IcdP	BGhIP
PCL	98 ± 1	99 ± 2	102 ± 1	98 ± 1	90 ± 1	90 ± 2	94 ± 1	92 ± 3
PCL AC	109 ± 4	97 ± 4	92 ± 3	91 ± 3	87 ± 3	61 ± 6	89 ± 3	84 ± 7
PA6	68 ± 11	48 ± 17	45 ± 16	40 ± 20	39 ± 15	108 ± 3	41 ± 20	35 ± 25
PA 11 AC	97 ± 1	98 ± 1	94 ± 1	92 ± 2	90 ± 3	93 ± 3	86 ± 7	85 ± 6
PBT	92 ± 1	87 ± 1	89 ± 1	88 ± 1	80 ± 1	60 ± 2	84 ± 4	81 ± 2
PPS	88 ± 2	100 ± 1	92 ± 1	93 ± 1	80 ± 2	101 ± 10	99 ± 3	97 ± 2
PHB:PP	10 ± 21	12 ± 22	17 ± 18	21 ± 16	19 ± 17	13 ± 14	26 ± 24	24 ± 18
PI	107 ± 1	113 ± 4	94 ± 2	86 ± 2	82 ± 1	29 ± 5	83 ± 10	65 ± 4

Fig. 4. Heatmap showing the mean recovery percentage of 8 analytes across different polymer nanofibers. The rows represent the types of nanofibers, and the columns represent the analytes. The colors indicate the recovery levels for each analyte (blue = lowest, red = highest). Each data point represents the mean recovery ± RSD (n = 6 extractions).

steric or desorption limitations reduce the efficiency with the larger molecules. PPS demonstrated excellent performance, with recoveries ranging from 80 to 101 %. It outperformed all other polymers for the most hydrophobic, high-ring-number PAHs (DahA, BghiP, IcdP). This superior performance is likely due to the high density of aromatic rings in PPS, which enable efficient π - π stacking with planar PAHs. Meanwhile, while the sulfur atoms do not impose significant steric hindrance, allowing for a close approach to the polymer backbone [34]. Based on their consistently high recoveries, low RSD values between manually prepared discs, and broad applicability across analytes, MB PCL, and PPS, which were the best aliphatic and best aromatic nanofibers, respectively, were selected as the most efficient SPE materials for further comparison.

3.2. Analyte interactions

A comparison with our previous study concerning the extraction of various xenobiotics (e.g. chlorophenols, nitrophenols, and pesticides) highlights the effect of analyte structure on the sorbent extraction performance [35]. In both studies, PCL emerged as one of the best-performing materials, providing nearly quantitative recoveries for most analytes. This confirms its versatility for a broad range of lipophilic compounds due to its hydrophobic character [28,29].

PBT performed poorly for chlorophenols (5–33 % recovery) but efficiently extracted permethrin (84 %). However, for PAHs, PBT achieved higher recoveries across a wide log P range, likely because the aromatic terephthalate units can engage in strong π - π stacking interactions with planar, polycyclic PAHs. Similarly, PI showed moderate recoveries for chlorophenols (53–68 %), higher recoveries for fenoxycarb (79 %) and permethrin (90 %), and even better performance for PAHs, consistent with π - π stacking interactions. PI contains lone electron pairs on oxygen and nitrogen atoms, as well as π electrons in C = O bonds and aromatic rings. This provides affinity for electron-rich PAHs through π - π and p- π stacking [30].

Although chlorophenols are aromatic, they contain only a single ring with -OH or -Cl substituents. While these groups can enhance π - π interactions [36,37], π - π stacking is likely not the dominant interaction for chlorophenols, as it is for PAHs, which have multiple fused aromatic rings provide larger planar surfaces for stronger π - π stacking. Instead, chlorophenol sorption is likely dominated by a combination of hydrophobic interactions, hydrogen bonding, and π - π stacking which explains why their recoveries are lower than those of PAHs [38]. This is consistent with studies showing that the strength of π - π interactions increases with the number of fused rings, enhancing the sorption of planar PAHs relative to single-ring aromatics [37,39].

PA11 displayed systematic increase in chlorophenols recovery with increasing lipophilicity, from 32 to 49 % for 2- and 4-chlorophenol to 79 % for bisphenol A, 84 % for fenoxycarb, and 100 % for permethrin. This highlights the significant role of hydrophobic interactions and explains PA11's high efficiency for PAHs.

PA6 performed well for chlorophenols in the previous study but poorly for PAHs (<50 %) in the present work. This discrepancy may be due in part to solvent effects, as PA6 swells in acetonitrile. However, it could also reflect weaker interactions with planar aromatic compounds, which primarily rely on π - π stacking. In contrast, hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions play a stronger role in extraction of chlorophenols. PA6 contains both amide (-NH) and carbonyl groups that can act as hydrogen-bond donors and acceptors, which further strengthen its interactions. Blend polymer PHB:PP (50:50) efficiently extracted permethrin and fenoxycarb (100 % and 70 %, respectively) previously, but it showed poor recovery for PAHs, despite similar log P values. PHB contains ester linkages with -O- and carbonyl groups that can participate in hydrogen bonding. Although these interactions may be less favorable for nonpolar, π -stacking-driven compounds, such as PAHs.

Overall, these results highlight the critical dependence of the extraction performance of polymer nanofibers on the combination of

hydrophobic, π - π , and hydrogen bonding interactions. The stronger π - π interactions in planar, multi-ring PAHs explain their higher recoveries compared to those of single-ring chlorophenols, for which hydrophobic and hydrogen bonding effects are more influential.

Given the differences in how aliphatic PCL and aromatic PPS interact with PAHs, we selected these sorbents to compare their analytical performance and further evaluate their efficiency in extracting multi-ring aromatic compounds.

3.3. Optimization

Detailed optimization of the key extraction parameters, including centrifugation conditions, desorption solvent, and volume, was conducted using PCL MB as the representative sorbent, since we expected comparable trends for all polymers (Fig. 5.). All optimization conditions were evaluated in six independent extractions ($n = 6$). Fig. 5 shows the mean values, and the error bars represent the relative standard deviation (RSD). Some calculated recoveries exceed 100 %, which occurs due to small variations in detector response and matrix effects. These values should be interpreted as nearly complete analyte extraction rather than true over-recovery.

In our previous report, we optimized several parameters, including the volume of the activation solvent, the sample volume, the centrifugation time, the centrifugation speed, the elution solvent, and the volume of the elution solvent [35]. Since the earlier work found that 200 μ L activation solvent volume, 600 μ L sample volume, and 10 s centrifugation time were sufficient, these parameters did not change in the present study.

The effect of centrifuge speed on analyte recovery was investigated at speeds ranging from 500 to 8000 rpm (30 – 7200 g, Fig. 5A.). MB nanofibrous discs are highly permeable allowing the sample to pass through the sorbent even before being placed in the centrifuge. ANOVA single-factor analysis showed that the speed significance increased with analyte lipophilicity. For the least lipophilic analyte, ANT, ANOVA indicated no significant effect of speed ($p = 0.88$). For the more lipophilic analyte PYR, the effect was marginal ($p = 0.06$), while for the highly lipophilic analyte CHR, the effect was significant ($p = 0.0006$). The highly lipophilic compounds BkF, BaP, DahA, and BghiP showed very strong significance ($p = 4.22 \times 10^{-6}$, 3.38×10^{-7} , 7.28×10^{-9} , and 6.60×10^{-7} , respectively), suggesting that the influence of centrifugation speed increases with analyte lipophilicity. Recoveries generally increased as the speed of centrifugation increased from lower values, reaching a maximum at approximately 4 000 rpm. This enhancement is likely due to more effective elution and desorption of strongly retained analytes because faster spinning improves solvent penetration through the fiber matrix and facilitates the removal of residual water, which can dilute the elution solvent. At very high speeds (e.g., 8 000 rpm, 7 200 g), recovery decreased slightly, potentially due to reduced interaction time with the sorbent, which can reduce desorption efficiency. Based on these observations, 4 000 rpm was determined to be the optimal centrifugation speed.

The volume of elution solvent is critical to both extraction efficiency and achieving a high enrichment factor. Smaller elution volumes enhance the pre-concentration of the analytes. However, an insufficient volume of extraction solvent results in incomplete desorption from the sorbent. Therefore, it is important to strike an optimal balance between maximizing the pre-concentration factor and ensuring full recovery. We evaluated the use of different volumes of acetonitrile, ranging from 100 to 600 μ L, to elute analytes from PCL discs. We calculated pre-concentration factors by comparing the peak areas of the analytes in a 5 μ g L⁻¹ standard solution to the areas obtained after extraction with different elution volumes. We determined recovery by comparing the expected pre-concentration to the actual observed values.

Eluting with 600 μ L of acetonitrile yielded nearly complete recovery of all analytes. However, the large volume reduced the achievable pre-concentration factor. Reducing the volume to 300 μ L still allowed for

Fig. 5. Effect of centrifugation speed (A), elution solvent (B), and elution solvent volume (C) on percent analyte recovery from PCL discs. Each condition was measured in six replicates ($n = 6$). Error bars indicate relative standard deviation (RSD, %).

exhaustive elution (87–105 % recovery) and increased the preconcentration factor to 1.7–2.1 (Fig. 5B). Further decreases in elution volume beyond 300 μL led to lower recoveries, particularly for the more hydrophobic analytes. These analytes are more strongly retained by the sorbent and require sufficient solvent for effective desorption. Based on these findings, 300 μL was determined to be the optimal elution volume, striking a balance between high preconcentration and efficient analyte recovery.

To prevent loss of the analyte, the elution solvent must have sufficient elution strength to elute the analytes, particularly since PAHs are highly hydrophobic. Additionally, it is important to consider that some polymers, such as PCL, can swell or dissolve in organic solvents. We tested methanol and acetonitrile as elution solvents and found that the shape of the PCL fibers did not change in either solvent (Fig. 5C.), which resulted from the short contact time during centrifugation. ANOVA analysis again revealed an increasing trend of significance with analyte lipophilicity. However, no significant solvent effect was observed for ANT, ($p = 0.18$). In contrast, the effect was significant for PYR ($p = 0.015$), and even stronger for CHR ($p = 0.0001$). The highly lipophilic compounds BkF, BaP, DahA, and BghiP exhibited very strong significance ($p = 2.07 \times 10^{-7}$, 6.43×10^{-7} , 9.80×10^{-7} , and 7.03×10^{-8} , respectively). These results suggest that the choice of elution solvent is increasingly important for more hydrophobic analytes. Use of acetonitrile provided higher recovery and more complete extraction, with 90–100 % recovery across analytes. Methanol, on the other hand, was 6–18 % less efficient. Based on these results, acetonitrile was chosen as the optimal elution solvent.

3.4. Analytical performance of the extraction and chromatography method

The analytical performance of two nanofibrous sorbents (PCL and PPS) was systematically evaluated across eight target analytes using real river water spiked at different concentration levels. Validation included limits of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ), the linearity, the determination coefficient (R^2), the repeatability (RSD), the preconcentration factor, the recovery, and the working range. Tables 1 and 2 summarize the results, while Supplementary Tables S-5, S-6 present the full data obtained from spiked river water at multiple concentration levels. This allows assessment of matrix effects and adsorption performance. The HPLC system suitability test is reported in the Supplementary material, Table S-7.

Matrix effects were evaluated by analyzing river water spiked with PAHs at different concentration levels (Table S-5, S-6). Negligible variability in recoveries was observed at the lowest and middle spiking levels for certain analytes. For example, ANT and PYR showed slightly lower recovery at the lowest concentration on PCL. In contrast, recovery of BghiP surpassed 100 % at the lowest concentration, potentially due to detector variability or matrix effects. On the PPS, the 1, 2, and 3 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ concentration points of ANT and PYR showed lower recoveries. Nevertheless, overall recoveries were consistent, and RSDs remained below 13.9 %, indicating that matrix effects were not significant and that both nanofibrous sorbents provided reliable extraction across the studied concentration range. The absence of recovery loss at higher spiking levels suggests that the adsorption capacity of the nanofibers was not exceeded under the studied conditions.

The LOD and LOQ were calculated from the calibration curve slopes using the formulas $\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \text{SD}/\text{slope}$ and $\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \text{SD}/\text{slope}$,

Table 1

Validation parameters for the HPLC method covering the spin filter extraction using 3 mm thick PCL discs.

Analytes	LOD [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$]	LOQ [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$]	Calibration plot $y = ax + b$	Determination coefficient ^a [R^2]	Recovery ^b [%]	RSD ^c [%]	Preconc. Factor ^d
ANT	0.009	0.026	$y = 100377x - 3372.1$	0.9998	102	1.1	2.0
PYR	0.014	0.041	$y = 93562x - 2644.7$	0.9998	98	1.2	2.0
CHR	0.014	0.042	$y = 76654x - 3539.4$	0.9996	96	1.7	1.9
BKF	0.019	0.058	$y = 46886x - 3794.7$	0.9990	92	1.3	1.8
BAP	0.026	0.078	$y = 106869x - 8931.9$	0.9984	85	1.8	1.7
DaHa	0.032	0.098	$y = 57001x - 3601.6$	0.9972	81	2.1	1.6
IcdP	0.14	0.42	$y = 9390.8x - 2775.1$	0.9989	59	7.9	1.2
BGhiP	0.096	0.29	$y = 42321x - 4266.4$	0.9990	57	9.5	1.1

^a Linearity range: 0.1 – 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, except IcdP and BGhiP 0.5 – 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.^b Recovery at a concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (direct injection of standard compared with spiked river water after extraction, elution volume 600 μL).^c n=6, 6 extraction rounds on same spin filter at concentration 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.^d Direct injection of standard compared to sample after extraction (elution volume 200 μL) at concentration 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.**Table 2**

Validation parameters for the HPLC method covering the spin filter extraction using 3 mm thick PPS discs.

Analytes	LOD [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$]	LOQ [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$]	Calibration plot $y = ax + b$	Determination coefficient ^a [R^2]	Recovery ^b [%]	RSD ^c [%]	Preconc. Factor ^d
ANT	0.024	0.072	$y = 99669x - 505.3$	0.9997	88	13.9	1.8
PYR	0.021	0.063	$y = 87838x + 2105.5$	0.9999	97	11.6	1.9
CHR	0.025	0.077	$y = 74705x + 4277.4$	0.9990	106	8.9	2.1
BKF	0.017	0.050	$y = 47284x + 2280$	0.9979	108	8.4	2.2
BAP	0.012	0.038	$y = 139206x + 2686$	0.9993	108	8.6	2.2
DaHa	0.029	0.088	$y = 60118x + 4536.4$	0.9970	113	8.2	2.3
IcdP	0.27	0.81	$y = 8398.1x + 1728.3$	0.9788	139	9.0	2.8
BGhiP	0.087	0.26	$y = 37275x + 3866$	0.9972	96	10.1	1.9

^a Linearity range: 0.1 – 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; IcdP 1 – 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; BGhiP 0.5 – 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.^b Recovery at a concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (direct injection of standard compared with spiked river water after extraction, elution volume 600 μL).^c n=6, 6 extraction rounds on same spin filter at concentration 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.^d Direct injection of standard compared to sample after extraction (elution volume 200 μL) at concentration 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

where SD is the standard deviation of six replicate measurements at the lowest calibration point for each analyte. This method enables direct comparisons of sensitivity among different sorbents and provides results consistent with the conventional signal-to-noise approach. For PCL, the LOD ranged from 0.009 to 0.14 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and the LOQ from 0.026 to 0.42 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. An increasing trend in LOD with analyte lipophilicity was observed, with IcdP showing the highest values, likely due to its weaker native fluorescence signal. For PPS, the LOD were slightly higher overall (0.012–0.27 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and the LOQ were 0.038–0.81 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The lowest LOD was obtained for BaP, while the highest corresponded again to IcdP. Overall, the PCL sorbent demonstrated lower detection limits, indicating slightly better sensitivity.

The calibration curves showed good linearity for both sorbents. Linearity was assessed by plotting peak area against analyte concentration. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was then used to evaluate the linear response. For PCL, the linear range was 0.1–5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for most analytes, except for IcdP and BGhiP, which was 0.5–5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The range for PPS was also 0.1–5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, except for IcdP and BGhiP, which were 1–5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 0.5–5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively. The determination coefficients were consistently high (PCL: $R^2 > 0.9972$; PPS: $R^2 > 0.9970$). The only notable exception was IcdP on PPS ($R^2 = 0.9788$), which again reflects its weak detector response.

Method accuracy was evaluated using recovery experiments with river water spiked with PAHs at various concentrations and expressed as percent recovery of the analytes relative to the spiked concentrations. Recovery (%) was calculated as the ratio of the amount of analyte extracted from the spiked river water to the amount added, multiplied by 100. At 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, PCL recovery ranged from 57 to 102 %, with the highest value observed for ANT, the least lipophilic analyte. Recovery decreased with lipophilicity and aromatic ring number, consistent with weaker interactions between hydrophobic analytes and the aliphatic PCL matrix. PPS showed higher recoveries overall (88–139 %). ANT and

PYR recoveries were slightly lower on PPS than on PCL. However, strongly aromatic analytes were better recovered on PPS, consistent with π - π interactions between the sorbent and multi-ring structures. The maximum recovery of 139 % may reflect experimental variability, co-extraction of matrix components, or detector fluctuations caused by changes in the excitation/emission wavelengths switching.

Repeatability was expressed as the relative standard deviation (RSD, %) of six replicate extractions. The extraction method precision was better for PCL (RSD = 1.1–9.5 %) than for PPS (RSD = 8.2–13.9 %). For PCL, RSD increased with analyte lipophilicity. For PPS the highest RSD values were observed for ANT, PYR, IcdP, and BGhiP. These results suggest that PPS provides stronger sorption for polyaromatic analytes, albeit with less reproducible performance than PCL.

The enrichment factors followed the expected pattern given the twofold sample-to-elution volume ratio applied. These factors were calculated by dividing the analyte concentration in the extract by the initial analyte concentration in the sample. PCL achieved values ranging from 1.1 to 2.0, while PPS ranged from 1.8 to 2.8. The slightly higher factors observed for PPS suggest stronger sorbent-analyte interactions, likely facilitated by its aromatic backbone.

Potential interferences from co-extracted matrix components were evaluated by analyzing blank river water and river water spiked with PAHs. Fig. 6 demonstrates a representative chromatogram that compares a blank river water, the same water that was spiked at 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (direct injection), and extracts that were obtained with PCL and PPS. Analysis of the blank river water confirmed the absence of interfering peaks at the retention times of the target analytes. Direct injection produced weaker signals, whereas extraction yielded stronger, more consistent peak intensities, reflecting the twofold enrichment. This improvement was most evident for more lipophilic analytes, for which PPS produced stronger responses.

In our previous work, we investigated the memory effect of the

Fig. 6. Chromatograms of the separations of analytes in $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ spiked river water obtained after the direct injection (purple line) and after the spin filter preconcentration and cleanup using PCL nanofibrous discs (green line), and PPS (blue line), and blank river water (orange line).

nanofibrous sorbents by repeating extractions using the same disc. No analyte carryover was observed [35]. In the present study, the discs were reused during the validation and real sample measurements, and no residual signals were detected after elution. While a systematic long-term lifetime study was not conducted, these observations indicate negligible memory effects and suggest that the sorbents can be safely reused.

In summary, both the PCL and the PPS nanofibrous sorbents demonstrated satisfactory analytical performance in the extraction of PAHs from river water. PCL generally provided lower detection and quantification limits, more consistent linearity, and superior precision, making it a reliable option for routine monitoring. PPS, on the other hand, exhibited higher recoveries and preconcentration factors, particularly for highly aromatic and lipophilic analytes. Overall, PCL provided robustness and reproducibility, while PPS enabled enhanced sensitivity and stronger analyte–sorbent interactions. The choice of sorbent depends on whether sensitivity or precision is prioritized in the analytical application.

3.5. Comparison with other extraction methods

Compared with the other PAH extraction approaches summarized in Table 3., the proposed method based on meltblown PCL discs offers

Table 3

Comparison of proposed methods with others reported in the literature.

Analytes	Extraction/ Analysis Method	Extraction Sorbent	Sorbent amount [mg]	Extraction/ Analysis time [min]	Steps	Recovery [%]	RSD [%]	Ref.
Naph, Ace, Fl, Phe, ANT, Flt, PYR, BaA, CHR, BbF, BkF, BaP, DahA, BghiP	SPE/LC-FD	C18	1000	-/40	7	60–93	3.2–9.9	[7]
Nap, Flt, BaF, PYR, BaP, ANT	PT-SPME/LC-FD	DE/COFs	10	-/-	5	87–116	1.2–9.7	[10]
Flu, Flt, PYR, CHR, BkF, BaP, DahA	NH-IS- μ -SPE/LC-DAD	Al-MOG and Zr-MOG	2–10	-/-	11	78–118	2.1–5.0	[11]
Nap, AcPy, ACP, Flu, Phe, ANT, FL, PYR, BaA, CHR, BbF, BkF, BaP, IcdP, DahA, BghiP	SPE by centrifugation/ GC-MS	C18	200	-/69	5	70–85	1.0–14.0	[12]
ACP, ANT, PYR, CHR, BkF, BaP, DahA, IcdP, BghiP	Online-SPE/LC-FD	PA4/6 NF	20	1/13	1	92–105	1.5 – 6.7	[9]
ANT, PYR, CHR, BkF, BaP, DahA, IcdP, BghiP	SC- μ SPE/LC-FD	PCL NF	25	0.5/11	3	57–102	1.1–9.5	This work

Acenaphthene (AcP); Acenaphthylene (AcPy); Anthracene (Ant); Benzo[a]anthracene (BaA); Benzo[a]pyrene (BaP); Benzo[b]fluoranthene (BbF); Benzo[g,h,i]perylene (BghiP); Benzo[k]fluoranthene (BkF); Chrysene (Chr); Covalent Organic Frameworks, Schiff-base on diatomaceous earth (DE/COFs); Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene (DahA); Diode Array Detection (DAD); Fluoranthene (FL); Fluorene (Flu); Fluorescence Detection (FD); Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS); Indeno [1,2,3-cd]pyrene (IcdP); Liquid Chromatography (LC); Metal Organic Gel (MOG); Naphthalene (Nap); Nanofibers (NF); Phenanthrene (Phe); Pipette Tip Solid Phase Microextraction (PT-SPME); Polyamide 4/6 (PA 4/6); Polycaprolactone (PCL); Pyrene (Pyr); Solid Phase Extraction (SPE); Needle hub-in-syringe Micro Solid Phase Extraction (μ SPE).

several advantages. PCL is a biodegradable sorbent that can easily be cut and packed into a spin filter format, making manufacturing and scaling up straightforward, unlike more complex materials such as Al-metal organic gels or covalent organic frameworks. Only 25 mg sorbent is required, and the three-step extraction procedure (10 s each) is completed in 30 s, excluding the time needed for pipetting and transferring to and from the centrifuge. The total analysis time is 11 min. This represents a substantial reduction compared to other reported protocols, which require 40 to 69 min. Additionally, the method is compatible with the parallel processing of up to 48 samples depending on the centrifuge configuration, which increases throughput. Although the protocol is not fully automated, it reduces the number of steps compared to conventional solid phase extraction, pipette tip solid phase microextraction, and solid phase microextraction workflows. High recoveries and low RSD values were obtained, confirming the method's reliability. Assessment of its environmental impact using the AGREEprep greenness score (Fig. 7.) yielded a value of 0.64, with limitations identified for points 1, 7, and 9 [40]. Lower scores were linked to criterion 1 because the samples are transferred to the laboratory instead of being prepared in situ, criterion 7 because of some manual handling although the number of steps is limited, and criterion 9, because HPLC is used for analysis. However, the use of fluorescence detection instead of mass spectrometry reduces energy consumption and environmental impact. Overall, the meltblown PCL sorbent provides a faster, and more practical alternative for PAH extraction.

Fig. 7. AGREEprep greenness score calculation [40].

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that meltblown PCL and PPS nanofibers are effective sorbents for rapid spin-filter micro solid phase extraction of PAHs from river water. Biodegradable PCL provided strong overall retention through hydrophobic interactions, while aromatic PPS exhibited enhanced affinity for higher-ring PAHs due to additional π - π stacking. The novel spin-filter format combines simplicity, short extraction time, and parallel processing capability, providing a practical alternative to conventional SPE approaches. Nanofibrous sorbents enabled high recoveries (57–139 %), low RSD values (RSD 1.1–13.9 %), wide linear ranges (0.1–5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for most analytes), and low detection limits (LOD < 0.27 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in real water matrices, indicating reliable performance. Assessment using AGREEprep (score 0.64) highlights the environmentally friendly character of the method. Although PPS enabled higher recoveries for the most hydrophobic analytes, PCL is a more sustainable option. Overall, the proposed approach highlights the potential of polymer nanofibers as versatile sorbents for extraction and analysis of hydrophobic contaminants in environmental samples.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ewelina Czyz: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Marie Štorková:** Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Jakub Erben:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Pavel Holec:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **František Švec:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Dalibor Šatínský:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.sampre.2026.100229](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sampre.2026.100229).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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